

Improvement of two-phase flow distribution in an evaporator header with the help of a Design Of Experiment

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of the experimental test campaign performed in a simplified version of an evaporator. The purpose was to determine the impact of several parameters on the distribution among the channels of the evaporator. The test matrix was created with the help of a design of experiment algorithm.

Keywords: Gas-liquid two-phase flow, multiphase flow metering, experimental, evaporators, distribution, Design of Experiment

1. Introduction

Vapor cycle systems are closed loops that can be used for equipment cooling and environmental control purposes such as air conditioning. They are composed of several key components (compressor, condenser, expansion valve,...). Among them, evaporators are continuously subjects of research to improve their efficiency by reducing their volume and increasing their overall aerothermal performances. One straightforward way to improve the heat exchange is to improve the flow distribution among the different channels of the evaporator. Indeed, flow misdistribution of the inlet two-phase fluid can cause up to 30% of thermal losses [1].

Unfortunately, the homogeneity of the distribution depends on many parameters with a varying range of impacts. The purpose of the present work is to examine multiple parameters and their combined effect.

Firstly, the main parameters influencing the flow maldistribution were gathered and analyzed. A list of features to study was defined, as well as their different levels [2]. It was then decided whether they could be expected to have a major or minor impact.

Many studies intended to assess their effects, and were gathered by several reviews [3; 4]. However, each study focus on a limited amount of parameter.

They follow the so-called one-factor-at-a-time (OFAT) strategy, which consists in varying each parameter over its full range, while the other variables are held constant. The optimal yield identified with these methods could not be the actual one, as the result fails to consider any possible interaction between the parameters [5].

In this context, the use of Design of Experiments (DoE) techniques fits perfectly. Indeed, these methods are used to understand how multiple input parameters (i.e. **factors**) and their interactions affect the response. The output obtained is displayed as a matrix, which defines, for every experiment, the **level** to be tested for each factor, i.e. the value of each parameter. Well chosen experimental designs *maximize the amount of "information" that can be obtained for a given amount of experimental effort* [6]. The settings of all parameters are varied simultaneously: trials are conducted throughout the potential experimental region, allowing to understand their combined effect on the response. In addition, it is possible to optimize

experimental effort. Indeed, in the extreme case, with the so-called "Full Factorial Design", every combination of factors and levels is analysed and, thus, the required resources become easily too high with respect to availability [7]. DoE techniques reduce the number of runs and analyze then the results by statistical methods, resulting in valid and objective conclusions [5]. Thus, secondly, a literature review about Design of Experiment (DOE) algorithms and their possibilities was carried out. In spite of the potentiality of DoE method in experimental application, it has a poor diffusion and is mainly applied in the industrial sector. Very few papers on the application of DoE in engineering research contexts have been found. In multi-phase flow applications, T.Sung et.al. [8] used DoE to optimally design a micro evaporator and Kim et.al. [9] to improve the hydrodynamic performances of a multi-phase pump. Both of them used "Fractional Factorial Design", which include only a portion of the runs specified for a Full Factorial. To the author knowledge, there are no existing studies in literature that applied DoE methods to the present process. Their usage could generate two advantages: (1) assessing the effect of the combination of all the desired parameters, both geometry and operating conditions, on the flow distribution, without needing to test all the possible sets of variables and thus, (2) reducing the required resources.

In parallel, a literature review about the multiphase flow metering was achieved. As the common flow separation technique was to be avoided, the venturi flow meters were selected as the most appropriate two-phase flow measurement technique. These instruments are very often coupled with a capacitance flow meter. However, the latter are not easily available and their design is operating condition-dependent. A new methodology of gas/liquid two-phase flow measurement by mean of a Venturi Flow Meter (VFM) solely was defined, and a calibration procedure was established. Ultimately, an adiabatic test bench was designed and built to be able to reach this objective. The main test section simply consists in a rectangular header connected to eight channels, on which a VFM is welded. As a result, this allowed for the correct measurement of the liquid and vapor phase distribution among the channels.

In a first time, the DOE purpose and the algorithm selected is detailed as well as its application to the present work. In a second time, the experimental setup is described, and the test matrix is as well presented. In a third time, the main results from this study are shown, analyzed and discussed.

2. Design of Experiment

Design of experiments is a systematic, efficient method used to plan an experimental campaign. DoE techniques reduce the number of runs required in an experimental campaign and analyze then the results by statistical methods, resulting in valid and objective conclusions [5].

The statistical theory underlying DoE generally begins with the concept of process models. Process modeling is the description of the variation of a response variable, y , by means of a mathematical function of one or more other quantities $f(x, \beta)$, and a random component, ϵ .

$$y = f(x, \beta) + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

The mathematical function consists of the predictor variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , which are observed along with the response, the parameters $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$, which are the quantities that will be estimated during the data analysis, and the error ϵ . For example, a linear model with two factors, x_1 and x_2 , can be written as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \beta_{12} x_1 x_2 + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

Here, the second and third terms on the right hand side are the main effect terms, and the fourth one is the two-way interaction term. Clearly, a full model could include many cross-product or interaction terms. However, in general these terms are not needed and most DoE techniques defaults to leaving them out of the model. In DoE applications, the set of x values to be tested can vary from one design to another. Indeed, some distributions of data in the x vector may yield better coefficient estimates (with minimal variation) than other x vectors.

For this reason, to efficiently design an experimental campaign, the objectives and the parameters in charge need to be clearly defined. In fact, depending on these two aspects, various existing DoE techniques can be applied in order to find the x vectors that give better coefficient estimates, for a given number of runs. The aim of the experiments could be choosing between alternatives (with *comparative experiments*), selecting key factors that affect the response (*screening experiments*), or even modelling a process (*response surface designs*) [6]. In the early stages of experimentation the analysis may be exploratory, to identify important sources of variability. Subsequently, the analysis is usually confirmatory in nature. Lastly, in some cases a mathematical model of the response can be developed [10]. However, all existing

DoE matrices have strict constraints on both the number of factors and the number of levels for each factor that can be handled.

A method that can be used regardless of the input parameters or the objective, is the D-Optimal criteria [6]. In addition, it can manage whatever process model, also with interaction and quadratic effects. The matrix form of the model reported in Equation

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

Here, for a main-effect model with n runs and k factors, \mathbf{Y} and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ are vectors with n components, \mathbf{X} is the model matrix of dimensions $[n \times (k+1)]$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is a vector with $(k+1)$ elements corresponding to the intercept β_0 and the k main effects. If also two-factor interactions are analysed, $k(k-1)/2$ estimates are added to the model.

The variance-covariance matrix of the vector of parameter estimates $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$, in a least-square analysis is equal to $\sigma^2(\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{X})^{-1}$. The variance parameter σ^2 is an unknown constant: when planning an experiment, σ^2 is set to one and only the elements of $(\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{X})^{-1}$ are considered. The diagonal elements of the variance-covariance matrix are the parameter estimate variances $\text{var}(\hat{\beta}_i)$. The off-diagonal elements are the covariances between pairs of estimates $\text{cov}(\hat{\beta}_i, \hat{\beta}_j)$ [11].

D-Optimal criteria minimizes the variance of the parameter estimates. The goodness of these experimental designs can be quantified by means of the *D-efficiency*.

$$\text{D-efficiency} = 100 \cdot \frac{1}{n \cdot \det((\mathbf{X}^T\mathbf{X})^{-1})^{1/p}} \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of runs and p is the number of estimates. This efficiency measures the goodness of a design relative to hypothetical orthogonal designs: indeed, for an orthogonal design, the variance-covariance matrix is diagonal and its determinant is equal to $1/n$. However these orthogonal designs might not exist: the efficiency is not useful as absolute measures, but should be used relatively, to compare one design to another for the same situation. Efficiencies that are not near 100% might be perfectly satisfactory. When D-efficiency is 100%, then the design is balanced and orthogonal [12].

3. Experimental setup and test matrix

3.1. Experimental setup

An air/water mixture is used as a fluid and the tests were carried at 7 bar bluto obtain a density ratio between the phases closer to the one typically encountered in refrigerants. Water is pumped from a tank by a

centrifugal pump (Wilo Helix V 214-1/16/E/KS/400-50) and its flow rate is measured with an electromagnetic flowmeter (Fuji Electric ModMAG® M1000). A 15 bar compressed air line is connected to the facility and its pressure is then decreased to around 6.5 barg through a pressure regulator. The air flow rate is measured thanks to a thermal mass flow sensor (CS Instruments VA 500). Air and water are then mixed together by mean of an elbow pipe inserted in the main water pipe. The schematic of the test facility can be found on the figure 1. The mixture is further sent to the test section.

Figure 1: Experimental apparatus

The facility is isothermal, as it was shown previously that heat transfer phenomena can be neglected in an evaporator header [13]. The test section (see Figure. 2) consists in a rectangular header made partly in aluminum and of dimensions 130mm x 186mm x 560mm. This manifold also exhibits two transparent faces to allow flow visualizations. The feeding tube is 1.5m long to ensure the two-phase flow development at the inlet of the test section. The diameter of the feeding tube can be varied to study its impact: 56mm I.D. (2") or 23mm I.D. (3/4"); as well as its position on the header: one horizontal position and 3 vertical positions. A visualization block made in Plexiglas is installed at the end of the feeding pipe to monitor the inlet flow patterns. Between the visualization block and the header, a removable device can be inserted. The design selected for this device was very similar to the one detailed by Ahmad et al. [14], which consists in a slightly curved and perforated thick plate. The objective of this accessory is to provide a pressure drop and break separated flow regimes such as stratified flow, and ensure a more uniform initial diphasic distribution. This accessory was additively manufactured in resin.

A DANTEC high speed camera was used to record the behavior of the air/water mixture inside the header.

Figure 2: Test section design

The latter is then connected to eight stainless steel channels of 10 mm I.D.. The channels can be inserted inside the header, by 0 , $\frac{1}{4}$ or $\frac{1}{2}$ of the header height, to study its influence. A VFM is welded on each channel. A straight pipe length of $50D$ is ensured ahead of the VFM, to allow for the development of the flow. A picture of the test section can be seen on FIG. 3. Besides, the fluid total pressure was monitored inside the water and air inlet pipes, inside the header, and inside each of the eight channels. The fluid total temperature was monitored at the water and air inlets. A safety valve is also installed on the header to ensure that the pressure inside the test section do not exceed 8 bar. The air/water mixture is further gathered from the eight channels through a collector and then exits the test section. The orientation of this whole assembly composed of the inlet feeding tube, the header, the eight channels and the collector can be changed.

Figure 3: Actual simplified evaporator

Venturi Flow Meter were selected to allow the measurement of the liquid and vapor phase mass flows in each of the eight channels. All the venturi of the present study were designed at the Von Karman Institute (VKI), following the standard NFEN ISO 5167-4. The four upstream pressure taps were interconnected in a triple T arrangement as recommended in the ISO 5167-4 and connected to one side of a pressure membrane sensor (Validyne DP15). Similarly, the four throat pressure taps were also interconnected in a triple T arrangement and connected to the other side of the sensor. The pressure difference measured by the membrane corresponds to the throat pressure drops ΔP_{TP} . All these instruments were connected to a NI DAQ (National Instrument) hardware, to acquire their signals at a frequency of 200Hz and during 90s. Thus, in total, eight pressure membrane instruments were used, to obtain the throat differential pressure drop of the eight VFM.

After the test section, the air/water mixture is again collected and sent back to the reservoir. A back pressure valve is present to set and control the targeted pressure inside the test facility.

3.2. Test matrix

In the present case study, the combination of factors and levels in charge made it impossible to choose an already existing experimental design. In fact, the problem involved 3 factors with 3 levels and 2 factors with 2 levels (Table 1). It was thus necessary to find a non-conventional way to define the experimental matrix.

Table 1: Factors, numbers and descriptions of levels for the specific tests case

Factors	Levels	Value
Inlet Tube Position	3	Position -1: horizontal inlet Position 0: lateral vertical inlet Position 1: lateral central inlet
Channels Intrusion	3	Intrusion -1: 0 mm Intrusion 0: 33 mm Intrusion 1: 66 mm
Splashing Grid	2	Grid -1: grid not present Grid 1: grid present
Water Flow Rate	2	Water -1: $0.18 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ Water 1: $0.37 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
Air Flow Rate	3	Air -1: $6 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ Air 0: $18 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ Air 1: $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

The experimental matrix was created by means of the Python package DoEgen [15], which combines

optimality criteria and finds the best matrix for a given set of parameters in input. In particular, for a given design space, the program creates possible experimental matrix increasing the number of runs. For each case, it then computes 5 *efficiencies* that define how close the matrix is to an orthogonal one (Orthogonality), how well it is centered between factors (Center balance), levels (Level balance), levels in pairs of factors (Two-level balance) and factor-level pair combination (Two-level missing). In addition, it gives the D-efficiency for a main-effect (D-efficiency) and for a two-way interaction model (D1-efficiency).

The aforementioned efficiencies with increasing number of runs are shown in Figure 4. Although even 54 tests gave high coefficients, the optimal design required 72 runs and was therefore selected. Indeed, with this design, the efficiencies are slightly higher. In addition, all the combinations of geometric layouts are tested with 72 runs.

Figure 4: Matrix *efficiencies* with increasing number of runs

3.3. Test procedure

An additional challenge associated with experimentation in gas-liquid flows lies in wall pressure measurements. Indeed, these must be made with minimum flow disturbance and with the guarantee of the presence of a single phase in all pressure lines. Purging is a well-known technique to ensure that pressure lines are always filled with water. During preliminary tests, measurements were taken under the same flow conditions, with and without purging. From these measurements, it was confirmed that a high presence of bubbles in pressure lines introduced large distortions and non-repeatability of the signal. Thereby, the first step in the experimental procedure consisted in filling the channels with water and purging all the Valydine's pressure lines from air bubbles. Still, as soon

as the air started flowing through the circuit, small air bubbles were eventually going in the lines, but not significantly affecting the signal. This operation was repeated whenever a considerable amount of air bubbles were present in the pipes.

In addition, for each testing day, the *offset* measurement was taken for each Valydine. This consisted in the differential pressure acquired with the circuit still, and the pressure lines filled with water. Every measurement taken during each testing day was then subtracted by the respective *offset* value. This ensured no discrepancies between testing days (because of different atmospheric conditions) nor between channels (because of differences between pressure lines). Flow visualization of the entire header were recorded during the campaign by means of an high speed camera.

The distribution was defined in terms of the standard deviation of differential pressure along the 8 channels. Each signal was acquired for 80 seconds at a sampling frequency of 200 Hz and averaged. The output response was then computed by:

$$y = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\Delta p_i - \Delta p)^2}{N}} \quad (5)$$

Where n is the number of channels, Δp_i is the signal averaged for the i -th channel and Δp is the mean of all Δp_i values. The optimal configuration of parameters is thus the one that minimizes the output response. In addition, for each channel, the uncertainty associated with the calibration curves was estimated by assuming a t-student distribution for the fitting error considering a 95% confidence interval.

All values obtained are shown as uncertainty bars in the result section.

4. Results and discussion

The best flow distribution with horizontal inlet was identified by conducting confirmatory runs with the optimal set-up obtained in the previous analysis. The corresponding differential pressure along the 8 channels is shown in Figure 5 (blue-triangle line), compared to the worse case scenario (orange-squared line). To focus the attention only on the variation of Δp , for each of the two curves the corresponding average value along the 8 channels has been subtracted. As expected from the previous analysis, the output obtained from these additional configurations was found to be the best case. The red error bars indicate the uncertainty of each channel.

Figure 5: Variation of differential pressure among the channels for the best and the worse layout with horizontal inlet.

For what concerns vertical inlet, **the** optimal combination of parameters cannot be defined, as close response values were obtained with different layouts. For example, looking at Figure 6, similar results were experienced both with (blue-triangle line) and without (orange-square lines) the grid. Instead, the green-star curve is relative to the worse set-up, with *intrusion -1* and *grid -1*. In Figures 7 and 8, two header visualizations of some of the vertical best cases are shown: the first with central inlet and grid, the second one for lateral inlet without the grid.

Figure 6: Variation of differential pressure among the channels for some of the bests and the worse layout with vertical central inlet.

The last step usually performed in DoE is finding the estimates β_i that best fit the process model. By means of both graphical and analytical techniques, the less affecting contributions of the model can be identified and, if needed, neglected. Since the levels of all factors were scaled between -1 and 1, the parameter estimates β_i allow for the direct comparison of the factor effects: the higher their absolute value, the higher the effect on the response of their corresponding term. This quantifies what we were analysing in

Figure 7: Header visualization with vertical central inlet and splashing grid.

Figure 8: Header visualization with vertical lateral inlet without grid.

the DoE Mean and DoE Mean Interaction Plots.

The model described by Equation 2 was developed. Additional information on the preliminary analysis of modelling results can be found in the Editorial Note. 7 additional runs, with both optimal and not optimal layouts, have been conducted to verify the effectiveness of the model. The order of magnitude of the predictions was in line with the measured values. However, more investigations need to be explored to correctly verify its validity. Indeed, due to the (1) contrasting effect of variables for vertical or horizontal inlet and (2) not clear best configuration for the vertical case, the author feels that a high precision cannot be reached with so many variables. Further examinations are needed to verify and/or identify the range of validity and the effective accuracy of the model.

5. Conclusions

This report shows the methodology followed to plan an experimental campaign by means of Design of Experiments techniques, as well as the approach for the analysis of results. Tests were performed to assess the phases distribution of an air-water mixture in the channels of an evaporator header. The parameters in charge were both geometric (inlet pipe position, channels intrusion, presence of a splashing grid at the header inlet) and operating (water and air mass flows).

In all the tested configurations, increasing the channels intrusion resulted in a more balanced presence of phases in the channels. Globally, also the presence of the splashing grid enhances the phenomena.

Both these results were expected from literature studies. However, for what concerns the vertical case, the only parameter that plays a definitive role is the intrusion: with this layout, neither the presence of the grid nor the inlet vertical position have an influence on the response. Consequently, no further conclusions can be extrapolated regarding the optimal configuration of variables: the lowest results, all with similar order of magnitude, were experienced with different layouts.

The worse distribution was found with horizontal inlet position without the presence of the splashing grid. Indeed, in all the literature studies analysed, the coaxial feeding tube gave worse results with respect to the vertical. However, with this configuration the presence of the splashing grid has a strong effect, giving also the layout with lower variability of the response for all the operating conditions analysed. The response reaches the same order of magnitude of the best-vertical cases.

From the experimental campaign conducted it was not possible to find the optimal configuration over all the variables analysed, but rather a series of different layouts that all gave similar results. Only with horizontal feeding tube, the effect of each parameter is clear, and it is possible to define the best configuration to enhance phases distribution as the one with highest intrusion, presence of the grid, lower water and high air flow rate.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky2 Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 886698. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the Clean Sky 2 JU members other than the Union. This paper reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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